

STOCHASTIC MODELING OF THE MESOSCOPIC ELASTICITY TENSOR RANDOM FIELD FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS

J. Guilleminot^a, C. Soize^b, D. Kondo^a, C. Binétruy^c

^a Laboratoire de Mécanique de Lille-UMR CNRS 8107, USTL

Boulevard Paul Langevin, 59655 Villeneuve d'Ascq, France

johann.guilleminot@univ-lille1.fr, djimeddo.kondo@univ-lille1.fr

^b Université Paris-Est, Laboratoire Modélisation et Simulation Multi Echelle, MSME

FRE3160 CNRS

5, Boulevard Descartes, 77454 Marne-La-Vallée Cedex 2, France

christian.soize@univ-paris-est.fr

^c TPCIM, Ecole des Mines de Douai

941 rue Charles Bourseul, BP 10838 59508 Douai, France

binetruy@ensm-douai.fr

SUMMARY

This work is dedicated to the stochastic analysis of the elasticity tensor random field for composite materials at the mesoscale. Two probabilistic models are proposed and identified experimentally. The approaches are used to investigate the representative volume element size with respect to the mesoscopic spatial correlation lengths.

Keywords: probabilistic model, composite materials, Karhunen-Loève expansion, Polynomial Chaos expansion, representative volume element, random elasticity tensor.

INTRODUCTION

For some classes of materials, the size of the Representative Volume Element (RVE) can be much larger than the one of the domain typically used in experimental testing or structural applications. This is especially the case of some concretes or composite materials reinforced by (micrometric) inclusions, for instance. Consequently, the experimental characterization may depend on both the prescribed boundary conditions and the realization of the random medium (depending on how close to the RVE size the size of the volume under investigation is), defining the so-called *apparent* properties. This large amount of scatter typically yields an extensive use of safety factors in case of structural design, thus penalizing the use of new and/or complex heterogeneous materials. Then, one may be interested in modelling both the spatial and statistical fluctuations exhibited by the mechanical properties of such random media.

This work is precisely dedicated to the construction, experimental identification and use of a probabilistic model of the stiffness tensor random field at the mesoscale of a long-fibre reinforced composite. For this purpose, two kinds of approaches are considered.

PROBABILISTIC MODEL FOR THE ELASTICITY TENSOR RANDOM FIELD

Let $\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x})$ be the matrix-valued random field corresponding to the matrix representation of the stiffness tensor random field, indexed by a bounded set $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ and with values in the set of all the $n \times n$ real symmetric positive-definite matrices, denoted by $M_n^+(\mathbb{R})$.

The first approach is based on the probabilistic model for random elastic anisotropic microstructures that was recently proposed in [2] [3]. For all \mathbf{x} fixed, the random matrix $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x})$ can be written as:

$$\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}) = \underline{\mathbf{L}}(\mathbf{x})^T \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{x}) \underline{\mathbf{L}}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \underline{\mathbf{C}}(\mathbf{x}) = \underline{\mathbf{L}}(\mathbf{x})^T \underline{\mathbf{L}}(\mathbf{x})$ is the mean matrix and $\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{x})$ is a second-order homogeneous random field, indexed by Ω , with values in $M_n^+(\mathbb{R})$ and such that $E\{\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{x})\} = \mathbf{I}_n$ for all $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega$ (where \mathbf{I}_n is the $n \times n$ identity matrix and E denotes the mathematical expectation). More precisely, this random field is defined as the nonlinear mapping of $n(n+1)/2$ independent second-order centered homogeneous Gaussian random fields, called the *stochastic germs*. The definition of this mapping is provided in [2] [3]. For all \mathbf{x} fixed in Ω , the probability density function with respect to the measure $dG = 2^{n(n-1)/4} \prod_{1 \leq j < k \leq n} dG_{jk}$ of the random matrix $\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{x})$ can be constructed by using the Maximum Entropy Approach [7]. This technique allows the probabilistic model to be constructed by only considering the *available* information (see the references given above for a detailed presentation of the mathematical framework). In the case of a homogeneous random field, the model is defined by $dn(n+1)/2 + 2$ parameters, namely the mean matrix $\underline{\mathbf{C}}$, a parameter δ (independent of \mathbf{x} and n) allowing the level of statistical fluctuations to be controlled and the spatial correlation lengths of the stochastic germs. In practice, the mean matrix and parameter δ can be identified from the experimental trajectories by using classical statistical estimates, while the estimation of the spatial correlation lengths can be estimated:

- i. by constructing the mapping between the spatial correlation lengths of the mesoscopic random field and the correlation lengths of the stochastic germs;
- ii. by estimating the correlation lengths of the mesoscopic random field, making use of an algebraic approximation of the correlation function.

PROBABILISTIC MODEL FOR THE MESOSCOPIC VOLUME FRACTION RANDOM FIELD

In the second approach, the stiffness tensor random field is defined through a stochastic homogenization procedure. Indeed, it is assumed that the mesoscopic randomness is mainly induced by local volume fraction random fluctuations. Thus, it is proposed to construct a probabilistic model of the mesoscopic volume fraction and to determine in turn trajectories of the elasticity tensor random field from the realizations of the volume fraction by using a micromechanical approach. For this purpose, let $\mathbf{x} \rightarrow f(\mathbf{x})$ be the

mesoscopic volume fraction random field, indexed by Ω and with values in $[0,1]$. The truncated Karhunen-Loeve expansion of random field f reads [5]:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \underline{f}(\mathbf{x}) + \sum_{k=1}^M \sqrt{\lambda_k} \eta_k \psi_k(\mathbf{x}) \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \underline{f}(\mathbf{x})$ is the mean function; $\{\lambda_k\}_{k=1}^M$ and $\{\psi_k\}_{k=1}^M$ are the eigenvalues and eigenfunctions of the linear integral operator with covariance kernel, respectively. The set $\{\eta_k\}_{k=1}^M$ is a set of orthogonal random variables that are, in general, statistically dependent. Such an expansion is classically used in order to reduce the probabilistic dimension of the modelling by properly choosing the order of expansion M . Next, gathering all the random variables in a single random vector η with values in \mathbb{R}^M , let us consider the q -order polynomial Gaussian chaos expansion of η [6] [7] [8]:

$$\eta = \sum_{\gamma \in \mathbb{N}^m, |\gamma|=1}^q \mathbf{z}^\gamma \hat{\mathbf{H}}_\gamma(\xi) \quad (3)$$

where $\{\mathbf{z}^\gamma\}_\gamma$ is a set of deterministic vectors in \mathbb{R}^M , $\{\hat{\mathbf{H}}_\gamma\}_\gamma$ are the normalized multivariate Hermite polynomials and ξ is a m -dimensional zero-mean Gaussian random vector (with $E(\xi_i \xi_j) = \delta_{ij}$, δ_{ij} being the Kronecker symbol). Combining Eqs. (2) and (3) yields the final probabilistic representation of the volume fraction random field. From Eq. (3), it is seen that the identification of the random field basically consists in determining the set $\{\mathbf{z}^\gamma\}_\gamma$. The estimation of these coefficients can be a major difficulty and can be achieved by using the Maximum Likelihood Principle [9]. The identification then yields an optimization problem defined on a compact Stiefel manifold which can be solved by using a random search strategy (see [10] for a detailed discussion about the associated methodology).

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS AND IDENTIFICATION

The identification of the parameters of the two probabilistic models requires the determination of experimental realizations of both the volume fraction and stiffness tensor random fields at the mesoscale. Furthermore, we are also interested in relaxing some typical probabilistic assumptions, such as mean ergodicity. This implies that both the size and the number of samples have to be sufficiently large, making usual experimental techniques less attractive. Thus, it is proposed to identify the experimental trajectories by combining a micromechanical analysis with ultrasonic testing. Details about this procedure can be found in [1] and are briefly recalled hereafter. Let A be the mapping defining the relation between the elastic properties of a material (with known material symmetries), the density and the velocity of some ultrasonic waves propagating inside a given volume of this material. In the isotropic case and considering longitudinal waves, this function is simply defined as:

$$V_l = \sqrt{E / (2\rho(1 + \nu))} \quad (4)$$

where E , ν and ρ are the Young's modulus, the Poisson ratio and the density of the material, respectively. Next, let M be the function derived within a micromechanical framework and defining the relation between the elastic properties of the material and the volume fraction in reinforcement. It should be emphasized that beyond the RVE size, the definition of this mapping requires the use of a computational homogenization procedure, taking into account the dependence of the apparent properties on both the boundary conditions and the realization of the random medium. However, this would yield a prohibitive computational effort in the present case. The definition of the mapping M was then performed by using a mean-field homogenization technique (namely, the Mori-Tanaka scheme; see [1]). Finally, let H be the composed function $A \circ M$, defined from $[0,1]$ into $S \subset \mathbb{R}^+$. The experimental trajectories of the volume fraction and stiffness tensor random fields can be respectively determined as

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = H^{-1}(V_l(\mathbf{x})) \quad (5)$$

and

$$\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}) = M(f(\mathbf{x})) = M(H^{-1}(V_l(\mathbf{x}))) \quad (6)$$

for all \mathbf{x} fixed in Ω . This methodology was applied to a thermoplastic resin reinforced by E-glass long-fibers.

Identification of the volume fraction random field

The first experimental realization of the mesoscopic volume fraction is depicted on Fig. (1), where the level of spatial fluctuations is clearly shown. We then consider the volume fraction random field as the restriction of a homogeneous random field to domain Ω , allowing the mean ergodicity (m.e.) property to be studied. It is shown that the m.e. assumption can reasonably be used, depending on the definition of an admissible coefficient of variation of the spatial mean estimate. The estimation of the coefficients involved in the Chaos representation (3) was performed on a 8-node cluster. The convergence of both the Chaos representation of random vector η and Karhunen-Loeve expansion (2) of random field f was studied. In particular, it is shown that a third order Chaos expansion (with $m=5$) yields accurate results (see Fig. (1)).

Figure 1. Left: graph of $\mathbf{x} \rightarrow f^{\text{exp}}(\mathbf{x}, \theta_1)$. Right: convergence of the PDF of η_1 with respect to the order q of the Chaos expansion.

The comparison between the experimental PDF of the centered random variable $f(\mathbf{x}_2) - E\{f(\mathbf{x}_2)\}$ and the simulated PDF (determined from 50 000 Monte-Carlo simulations of the random field, see Eq. (2)) is provided on Fig. (2).

Figure 2. Experimental and simulated PDF of the random variable $f(\mathbf{x}_2) - E\{f(\mathbf{x}_2)\}$.

Identification of the stiffness tensor random field

The parameters of the probabilistic model of the elasticity tensor random field are identified from the experimental trajectories of $\mathbf{x} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x})$ (see Eq. (5)). The mean isotropic matrix was first computed by using a classical statistical estimate: $\underline{\mathbf{C}}_{11} = 5.33$, $\underline{\mathbf{C}}_{12} = 3.11$ (GPa).

The spatial correlation lengths of the mesoscopic stiffness tensor random field were determined by approximating the correlation function by an exponential-type model. The optimization problem was solved by using a stochastic pattern search algorithm, yielding the two following estimates: $L_C^x = 11.88$, $L_C^y = 8.26$ (mm). Next, the relation between the correlation lengths of the stochastic germs and the correlation lengths (L_C^x, L_C^y) of the mesoscopic random field was estimated. For the sake of simplicity, it was assumed that for all (i, j) (with $1 \leq i \leq j \leq 6$, see [3]), one has $l_{ij}^x = l_U^x$ and $l_{ij}^y = l_U^y$, so that only two spatial correlation lengths have to be identified. The mapping $l_U^k \rightarrow L_C^k$ (where k stands, either for \mathbf{x} or \mathbf{y}) was constructed and was shown to be linear: $L_C^k \approx 1.1l_U^k$. It can then be deduced that $l_U^x = 10.8$ and $l_U^y = 7.5$ (mm).

Furthermore, it was shown that estimating the dispersion parameter δ by using a simple statistical estimate yields artificially small values, because of the local isotropy of the experimental realization of the random field. In this context, this parameter was identified by using a specific calibration of the overall level of statistical fluctuations and was found to be such that $\delta = 0.0948$.

Finally, the probabilistic model for the mesoscopic stiffness tensor random field is completely defined by:

- The mean matrix (in GPa): $\underline{\mathbf{C}}_{11} = 5.33$, $\underline{\mathbf{C}}_{12} = 3.11$.
- The dispersion parameter, $\delta = 0.0948$.
- The correlation lengths of the stochastic germs (in mm): $l_U^x = 10.8$, $l_U^y = 7.5$.

PARAMETRIC PROBABILISTIC ANALYSIS OF THE RVE SIZE

The use of such mesoscopic probabilistic models in the definition of the RVE size is briefly illustrated in this section. Let us consider the probabilistic model for the elasticity tensor random field. For a given realization θ , let $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_i(\theta)$ be the realization of the apparent stiffness tensor associated with a volume V_i containing i^2 mesovolumes. Since we are interested in characterizing the probabilistic convergence, we will consider, for the sake of simplicity, a Voigt estimate of the apparent tensor: $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_i(\theta) = 1/i^2 \sum_{k=1}^{i^2} \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}_k, \theta)$. The parametric probabilistic convergence analysis can be performed by considering the convergence of the random variable $Z = N_i / E\{N_i\}$ with $N_i = \|\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_i(\theta)\|$ (see [2]). The convergence of the level of statistical fluctuations, as a function of the ratio between the size of the apparent volume V_i and the mesoscopic spatial correlation length, is depicted on Fig. (3), for different probability levels (0.9, 0.95 and 0.99).

Figure 3. Convergence of the level of statistical fluctuations for different probability levels.

It is seen that if one defines the RVE size with respect to a level of fluctuations less than 1%, the characteristic size (in a given direction) of the RVE is 10 (resp. 12 and 16) times the spatial correlation length of the mesoscopic random field, with probability level 0.9 (resp. 0.95 and 0.99). These orders of magnitude are in agreement with the ones provided in the literature (see [3] [11] for instance). It is worth noticing that in the case of the material considered in this study, this criterion would give a 2D-RVE of size 140 mm x 140 mm (while the usual tension zone in tensile tests is approximately ten times smaller, for instance).

CONCLUSION

This study was devoted to the computational and experimental identification of two probabilistic models that can be used for modeling the elasticity tensor random field at the mesoscale of reinforced composites. In particular, this identification required the design of an experimental methodology, allowing some typical probabilistic

assumptions to be tested. The relevance of both the probabilistic modeling and identification strategy was demonstrated by comparing the experimental results and a database obtained from numerical Monte-Carlo simulations. Finally, the use of such mesoscopic probabilistic model in the definition of the RVE size was illustrated.

REFERENCES

1. J. Guilleminot, C. Soize, D. Kondo and C. Binétruy, C. Theoretical framework and experimental procedure for modelling mesoscopic volume fraction stochastic fluctuations in fiber reinforced composites. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 45: 5567-5583, 2008.
2. C. Soize. Non-gaussian positive-definite matrix-valued random fields for elliptic stochastic partial differential operators. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 195: 26-64, 2006.
3. C. Soize. Tensor-valued random fields for mesoscale stochastic model of anisotropic elastic microstructure and probabilistic analysis of representative volume element size. *Probabilistic Engineering Mechanics*, 23: 307-323, 2008.
4. E. T. Jaynes. Information theory and statistical mechanics. *Physical Review*, 106(4): 620-630, 1957.
5. M. Loeve. *Probability Theory, 4th Edition*. Springer-Verlag, New-York, 1977.
6. R. Ghanem and P. D. Spanos. *Stochastic finite elements: a spectral approach*. Springer-Verlag, New-York, 1991.
7. C. Soize and R. Ghanem. Physical systems with random uncertainties: Chaos representations with arbitrary probability measure. *SIAM Journal of Scientific Computing*, 26(2): 395-410, 2004.
8. N. Wiener. The homogeneous chaos. *American Journal of Mathematics*, 60: 897-936, 1938.
9. R. J. Serfling. *Approximation Theorems of Mathematical Statistics*. John Wiley & Sons, 1980.
10. C. Desceliers, R. Ghanem and C. Soize. Maximum likelihood estimation of stochastic chaos representations from experimental data. *Int. J. Numer. Meth. Engng.*, 66: 978-1001, 2006.
11. X. F. Xu and X. Chen. Stochastic homogenization of random elastic multi-phase composites and size quantification of representative volume element. *Mechanics of Materials*, 41: 174-186, 2009.